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SUB-CONTRACTS AND INDIAN ECONOMY: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

Building the economic body of India is solely responsible for the prosperity of the country and country men, this journey has crossed many stages and is presently giving the feeling that the soul of economy is in outsourcing the services and offering the knowledge enable support. India is rich in natural resources at the same time it is getting richer in skills with specialisation in numerous unique expertise, though this is not the only responsible factor for restructuring the Indian Economy however quantum of development in terms of shifting over professional expertise looks like contributing for a dynamic economy and promotable economy with regards to the closest rival economy^[1]. This paper tries to examine the shape of Indian Economy in context with the first quarter of the century and resourceful ability to learn and acquire the leading position within the global leaders Also this has been concluded that by the end of the nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century, India has became the leader who is offering outsourcing of some very important business processes for conglomerates from developed economies.

Keywords: India and sub-contract; Outsourcing options; Trends in Outsourcing, Indian excellence in knowledge sharing.

INTRODUCTION

Today, India is widely recognized as a world-renowned location for offshore information and communication technology (ICT) services, and as home to many global firms specializing in Business Process Outsourcing (BPO)^[1]. Although India has been an attractive offshore location for multinational enterprises (MNEs) since the early 1990s, there have been doubts about prospects for attracting high-end functions such as research and development (R&D)^[8]. Indeed, the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) national innovation capability index placed India among the lowest third of the world for both 1995 and 2001 (UNCTAD, 2005). Yet, almost overnight, India has become a

favoured destination for R&D facilities. By 2005, India claimed half of the R&D projects destined for the Asia-Pacific region. A new pattern of R&D investment was also emerging, as noted most recently by business/management scholars; most R&D facilities in India focused on technology transfer, localization, and adaptation, and were initially driven by the availability of low-cost R&D personnel and in software, R&D meant engineers either developing custom software solutions, or code to be integrated into products for the global market. Today, however, evidence suggests that such orientation is shifting to technological innovation, particularly to cater to global markets. Following pioneers such as Texas Instruments, many global firms now have R&D facilities in India.

How does an economy, still mired in illiteracy and poverty, and with limited infrastructure, not only claim global leadership in some ICT sectors, but also emerge as a major location for R&D by MNEs? The development of the Indian software industry is well documented, particularly with respect to the role of the state and the emergence of software services, the role of MNEs, the role of local entrepreneurship and the role of Non-Resident Indians (NRIs) and the “new Argonauts” Since the onset of economic liberalization from the mid-1980s, the ICT sector spearheaded economic growth by capitalizing on two global trends: first, the rapid growth in demand for software and ICT services, and second, the shortage of a people with the necessary skills to meet the demand. Yet, while the literature sheds light on the initial growth and transformation of offshore services, the upgrading to high-level R&D capabilities is a relatively new and under-researched phenomenon. Potentially, this upgrading has broad implications for our understanding of innovation and its potential for economic transformation in emerging economies.

What we have observed in India is an emerging trend whereby R&D facilities increasingly target the Base-of-the-Pyramid (BOP) market. The BOP market refers to the estimated over 4 billion consumers, mostly residing in the developing world, with the lowest incomes [9]. They serve as a potentially vast and yet largely untapped market for MNEs, as the majority has yet to own a number of consumer products. Affordable cars by the Indian manufacturer Tata, or Unilever’s marketing of shampoos in micro-packages are among the examples of innovative practices originating from India. Increasingly, since then, the term “frugal innovation” has earned a double-meaning, one of low-cost R&D operation and another of products/services developed with an aim of significant affordability. MNEs view social issues in low-income countries as strategic opportunities providing “win-win” situations for them and the communities involved. The growing interest among MNEs toward the BOP market is also driven in part by the saturation of consumer markets in the developed world. This trend may not only have significant economic impacts but there is also welfare potential that emerging economies can exploit. It leads to the question of the distinctiveness of the Indian model of engagement with the global economy, and whether it offers an alternative avenue for economic transformation.

In this paper we examine the rationale for R&D location by MNEs, and analyze how they cultivate, access, and exploit market knowledge for product development. This paper draws on over a decade of observation and field research conducted in Bangalore. Interviews with four major MNEs were conducted in late 2007 and mid-2012, specifically, with executives of R&D facilities located in Bangalore, for their views on the location advantages offered by India. We draw on the case of Bangalore, which is routinely referred to in the International press by terms such as “Silicon Plateau”, because it exemplifies, in many ways, the process of upgrading in the Indian ICT industry.

EMERGING ECONOMIES AND RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Although R&D conducted away from the home economy has always constituted a small proportion of the total R&D investment, it has grown considerably in recent decades. Between 1965 and 1995, the proportion of R&D efforts conducted abroad grew from about 6% to 26%. In fact, R&D globalization has come to be viewed as strategically critical for MNEs in the latter half of the 20th century. Although it involves a sophisticated global coordination of localized skills, decentralized R&D has become central to the strategic competitiveness of MNEs.

Role of R&D location and Globalization

Until recently, globalization of R&D facilities has taken place almost exclusively in developed-world locations. The bulk of it comprised U.S. MNEs locating R&D facilities in Western Europe and Japan, European MNEs locating in Japan and the U.S., and Japanese MNEs in the U.S. and Europe. The concentration of R&D facilities in a select few locations in the developed world is particularly evident in the case of electronics and pharmaceuticals. This is no surprise, as the most important known determinants of overseas R&D location are:

- Quality of R&D personnel
- Intellectual Property Protection

➤ Presence of Collaboration with Universities

The relative absence of quality R&D personnel, a weak institutional environment and IP regime, and political and security risks, have so far deterred R&D investments in emerging economies.

It is only in recent years that assumptions about home economy-dominated R&D function have changed. For those firms that conduct R&D abroad, China and India have emerged as alternate R&D destinations. India is particularly interesting because of its profile. Although the per capita gross national income (GNI) of India is lower than that of China, and its consumer market is less developed, India attracted roughly half of R&D projects in the Asia-Pacific region by 2005.

India had the lowest labour cost for university-educated workers among 16 countries, according to a survey conducted by the McKinsey Global Institute. Furthermore, the average salary of engineers in India was \$13,580 compared to \$70,000 in the United States. They also worked the longest hours. Cost savings also come from low construction and support staff salaries, estimated at 70–75% and 30–40%, respectively, of those in the United States^[1]. However, there are disagreements about the quality of R&D personnel found in developing countries.

When it comes to the role of the domestic market growth potential in locating R&D facilities, however, the direct relationship is far from clear. This is especially because R&D facilities in emerging economies have, to date, focused on a limited set of functions. The available evidence about the extent to which domestic growth and R&D globalization are linked is contradictory. The Kauffman Foundation survey, for example, showed that the MNEs were reluctant to conduct R&D for new technologies aimed at new markets in emerging economies. Yet, given that sunk costs for MNEs are significant, particularly for R&D facilities, firms are unlikely to globalize R&D facilities based merely on media hype. Our previous studies in Bangalore also showed evidence of a growing local knowledge base, and increased “institutional thickness” for R&D activities in general, whether for MNEs, Indian MNEs, or local start-ups, even if most of the activities were oriented toward overseas markets. Thus, the dynamics of R&D globalization in developing countries and its links to the domestic market warrant investigation.

R&D Activities driven by new markets in Emerging Economies

So far, R&D globalization in emerging economies has been understood as an instrument of technology transfer. This is because R&D facilities in emerging economies typically focus on product adaptation to local markets (“localization”) or product development using existing technologies (“asset exploiting”), instead of basic research (“asset seeking” or “technology creating”). Product adaptation and development favour low-cost locations with proximity to production facilities, while for basic research, proximity to technological knowledge and lead markets is critical. Thus, it has been understood that basic research takes place exclusively in the developed world.

The most recent R&D decentralization, however, suggests that this configuration is changing. Developing countries have a renewed opportunity as favoured R&D locations. They are beginning to be viewed as laboratories where firms can learn and conduct R&D for products specifically targeted at the BOP market. The new configuration therefore involves targeting the BOP market as a “lead market,” which transforms the location attributes of R&D activities. R&D activities in emerging markets have therefore been characterized as distinctive, and understood as either a form of “resource constraint-innovation” or “value engineering”. Most recently, “reverse innovation” is proposed as a way to capture a possible reversal of technological transfer, from the conventional North to the South to the South to the North. This suggests, on the one hand, the maturity of innovative capacity on the part of some emerging economies (e.g., China and India), and on the other, an increasing receptivity of the North toward incorporating ideas originating from the Global South. This is in part due to the new economic reality of the post-crisis frugality, and in part due to the increasing recognition of heterogeneity of ideas as a basis for innovation in various niche areas of the market. As we shall show, learning from the Global South was a largely abstract idea for firms until a decade ago. But their stance has changed radically in recent years, so much so that it is becoming recognized as a realistic economic opportunity.

Innovation and Role of Proximity in Market knowledge

How does firm access, cultivate, and exploit information from the market and feed it effectively into product development? The inner workings of innovation remain surprisingly unknown even in the developed-world context. If innovation remains unpredictable, whether a new idea can lead to successful product development and commercialization adds yet another layer of mystery. Technological innovation is easier to track and to understand as a supply-side (scientific-knowledge)

process that is then diffused through various means (“technology transfer”). In contrast, how demand-side knowledge is incorporated into the process of innovation and product development remains under-theorized.

Many business and management scholars have recognized the role of the consumer in Innovation. There is a longstanding literature on producer-user interactions and user-led innovation. However, the literature on user-producer interactions largely assumes that users are known and specified and, due to methodological difficulties in substantiating and generalizing this process, research that acknowledges and focuses on the systematic role of the user in demand-defined contexts is scarce. Market knowledge is understood to be “tacit” and context-specific, and thus has strong geographical implications. The lack of market knowledge is often cited as a key reason for the failure to launch a new product overseas. Proximity to markets becomes essential for firms, as geographic distance tends to increase “noise” in communications, and raise cultural barriers. That partly explains why most inter-firm innovation occurs among domestic firms for home markets, and why off shoring poses challenges.

In discussing the notion of “being there”, introduced the literature on use producer interactions into geography by assessing the proximity preferences of industrial users. Gertler acknowledges user-producer interactions in inter-firm relations and “learning by- interacting” as important market knowledge inputs in the process of innovation.⁹ Furthermore, tacit knowledge is fundamentally spatial, as it is a key determinant of the geography of innovative activity in today’s globalized economies, precisely because the most effective “learning-by-interacting” requires a geographical venue, complete with face-to-face interactions.

R&D FACILITIES IN INDIA AND MNEs

The emergence of India as a preferred location for corporate R&D facilities defies conventional logic, as these functions have previously been conducted exclusively in the developed world. But access to other corporate headquarters, advanced producer service functions, highly skilled and broadly trained managerial workers (i.e., not just trained engineers), combined with the vast BOP market makes India a unique strategic location for marketing, market research, as well as R&D activities for MNEs. Our aim is to address the following question: what are the emerging geographical, functional, and organizational shifts that are observed in MNE R&D locations? To answer this question, we have examined how India’s R&D facilities have changed over time, and how firms are re-conceptualizing the benefits of decentralized R&D.

To gather information on the nature of innovation in India, we interviewed executives of four prominent MNEs with R&D facilities in Bangalore, India (three U.S. and one German firm). These interviews were conducted initially in December 2007 and the follow-up interviews took place in May 2012. They are designed to access data unavailable from institutional sources. More importantly, they were intended to assess the evolution of R&D facilities and their functions over time. Interviews are acknowledged as an effective tool for research on firms. Interviews have long been used to understand the location attributes of MNEs and the dynamics of R&D globalization.

Starting with India for R&D and its strengthening

As a corporate location, India has undergone a dramatic transformation, from a low-cost location only appropriate for low-end programming and processing, to a prime location that allows for high-end corporate functions including R&D and strategic marketing. Although India is now well known for its significant role in offshore software services and business process outsourcing, India’s emergence as an R&D location for MNEs is no more than a decade-old phenomenon. All our interviewees in 2007 agreed that their firms have begun viewing India as a prime location for R&D facilities only in recent years. Our interviewee from company A commented, “Innovation in India would have been inconceivable merely three years ago”. In another example, an Indian executive from company B commented, “It is only a few years ago we were able to convince the corporate level executives to locate R&D in India. Even today, the mid-level executives are still not convinced that we can do R&D effectively here”. Although company C has been in India since 1989, R&D work did not begin until February 2002, and they too claimed that they had earned the confidence of their headquarters only recently.

Company B conducts R&D in a more dispersed manner than Company D, and has centres in Canada, China, France, Germany, Hong Kong, Israel, India, Japan, Singapore, and the United States. Given that China was already the largest manufacturing location and the second largest market by 1998, it is perhaps no surprise that the firm made China a major R&D location as well. Within India, company B boasts five R&D centres, and the operation in Bangalore includes Research Labs, Software Group,

and the core Network Division. By 2007, India was their R&D hub, with 3,500 engineers, responsible for 40 percent of software used in its mobile phones worldwide.

Impact of Role of Proximity, market knowledge, and corporate hierarchy

What has not changed between 2007 and 2012 is that there has been a constant and strong belief in the advantages of conducting development locally. As the interviewee from company A offered, "What's important is that not only we manufacture locally, but also design locally."¹⁸ The interviewee from Company D commented, "There is no way that our headquarters (located in the United States) can suggest products for the poor. They simply do not have the intuition and the sensibility". The same interviewee also commented, "Proximity is important". It breeds intuition and market knowledge." These sentiments, and sometimes exact phrases, were also heard again in our 2012 interviews.

One example of Company C's efforts to address local potential is represented by its well-publicized involvement with a district in the state of Andhra Pradesh, where half the population of 300,000 lives in poverty. For Company C, whose products such as personal computers, scanners, and printers remain unaffordable to most Indians, the district served as a "learning lab" to understand community needs and better reflect newly acquired knowledge in the process of innovation. The lab continues its presence in Bangalore even after the project ended because, "We are inspired by the needs here. We have an advantage of being close to the market. Best research is done close to customers, and we have leading edge customers locally." These customers include local users in the BOP market as well as Indian MNEs.

Evidence also suggests that a local market orientation, which is often viewed rather simplistically as "localization" (minor adaptation of already existing products to local market needs) and inefficient (due to scale advantages of the global market), may, in some cases, nurture local innovative capabilities and improve the standing of local R&D facilities in the global corporate hierarchy. For example, Company C's R&D facility was somewhat unique and differed from a typical R&D facility when it was established a decade ago in India. Most other R&D facilities in India established by MNEs began by focusing on accessing Indian talent for global R&D. But the primary goal of Company C's R&D facility, since its inception, has been to cater to local market needs. As our interviewee commented, "R&D labs in India are often forced to focus on what I call 'lower hanging fruits in global research' by their headquarters. What we wanted to accomplish was a lot harder". Thus, the emphasis on talent at the expense of local market knowledge can have organizational repercussions that may in turn contribute to delaying the R&D capabilities of scientists and engineers located in India. Yet, the tension that existed between solidifying its legitimacy as a global R&D hub and catering to locally emerging markets was clear in the interview we conducted in 2007, as the reality of its operation was more accurately represented by the former (i.e., lower hanging fruits) than the latter (i.e., product development for local market needs). Such tension had dissipated by 2012, according to the recent interview.

All interviewees stressed that local autonomy is the key to successful innovation for the Indian market. Company A has reorganized its R&D facility to be comprised of one part that focuses on emerging markets and another that caters to the global market demand largely driven by the Global North, with the former commanding autonomy in decision making.²² Company C did not establish a separate India and/or emerging market division in its R&D facility; rather, it has its entire group consider emerging markets to allow cross-pollination of ideas between those oriented toward the Global South and the North. Company D's R&D facility is established as a research organization, and allows researchers to self-determine their own projects, with a division manager providing guidance. Autonomy in decision-making is not only important in shaping directions and determining the research agenda, but also in giving sufficient time for each project to reach fruition. As the interviewee from Company C aptly observed, "with emerging market products, you need to be absolutely patient because it takes far longer to see the outcomes of an idea". The executives of all firms interviewed invariably expressed the same view about conducting product/service development for emerging markets. While the solutions may not require breakthrough ideas, the way to find solutions to constraints may be quite unconventional.

Role of BPO Market Opportunities

India has a vast BOP market, and offers unique conditions that make it ideal for as a location for R&D oriented toward that market. As the executive from Company A pointed out "there is a huge market to improve rural health, whether it is Tele-medicine, water quality, energy issues, or diseases. The recognition was present in 2007, and in 2012 the firm is actively conducting R&D to fill the market demand. The executive we interviewed from Company B viewed the market as an "ecosystem" and commented, "To enhance technology adoption, you need to consider the entire ecosystem. When it comes to research, you need to interact with academia, identify research problems, talk to the

government for infrastructure, and interact with service providers". Our interviewee from Company D contrasted China and India as R&D locations for the BOP market as follows:

China is not interested in innovation for the poor, neither the government nor academics. In that sense, India is unique, it has the combination of (1) Availability of highly skilled personnel (2) Democratic Governance (3) Large potential market (4) Strong government interest. It also has a diverse, multi-lingual market. It is an ideal laboratory for the innovation for the poor.

CONCLUSION

The Indian market serves as an ideal laboratory and testing ground for new products and services that target emerging economies. All our interviewees agreed that India is an attractive laboratory for MNEs for many reasons. First, as markets in advanced industrialized economies have matured, MNEs are seeking alternative markets for growth. Second, India's inadequate infrastructure demands identification of needs and technological solutions that are difficult to conceive of, and turn into product ideas, for researchers in the developed world. Third, India's socially and culturally diverse environment serves as a laboratory of similar challenges faced in many other countries.

This constitutes, in effect, a new rationale for R&D location. Our research suggests that India is emerging as a key R&D location for BOP-oriented products, especially for MNEs. Given that R&D locations have been restricted to selected sites in the developed world until recently, the emergence of India as an R&D location demands our attention in order to gain a better understanding of the factors influencing global R&D location. Today, India's attractiveness is largely assumed to be cost-driven and/or skill-driven. While these are certainly necessary criteria, they alone are insufficient to make India an attractive R&D destination. MNEs are finding new advantages in conducting decentralized R&D in emerging economies to stimulate innovation and product development globally. Conducting innovation from India stimulates diversity in business models within the firm, as senior management in the U.S. and Europe has a different experience base. This suggests a new strategic importance for developing countries as locations of R&D activities, and as sources of market knowledge.

MNEs face challenges when entering the BOP market that have to do with operating in an unfamiliar market where existing metrics for "lead" users do not work. While not every economy in the developing world can take the path India has, for the first time what has long been perceived as India's weaknesses (poverty, an undeveloped consumer market, and weak infrastructure) is now viewed as a resource for R&D activities. Through this research, we hope to contribute to the literature on globalization of R&D facilities, and on the role of developing countries as locations for cultivating the BOP market.

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